

Trends in the Growth of Finances of Government of Himachal Pradesh from 1999-2000 to 2021-22

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The focus of the present empirical study is to investigate the growth of revenue and expenditure of the Government of Himachal Pradesh from 1999-00 to 2021-22. The annual average growth in different components of revenue account and capital account income and expenditure is calculated to understand the long run trends in finances of Government of Himachal Pradesh. The trends in deficit in the budgets of Government of Himachal Pradesh are analysed to find out the financial position of the state government in the recent decades. For this purpose we have compiled the component wise data on revenue and capital account receipts and expenditure from 1999-2000 to 2021-22 from various statistical abstracts of Himachal Pradesh. The results shows that the revenue receipts is growing with declining trend whereas revenue account expenditure showing fluctuations and stable increasing trend particularly expenditure on health and family welfare. The capital account income is maintained and expenditure is rising with fluctuations. It means greater liabilities of the state government in coming years. The expenditure on physical and social infrastructure is although increasing in successive years but it shows declining growth, which means budget, is more skewed towards revenue account expenditure. The long term trends of deficit shows that the state is heavily borrowing to meet its expenditure thereby increasing its liabilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that the debt of the Government of Himachal Pradesh has been rising continuously in the recent decade and the financial position of the government is worsening each year. The budget of the state government in the year 2023-24 reflects rupees 4704 crore as revenue deficit and estimated fiscal deficit is rupees 9900 crore, which is 4.6 percent of GSDP.

In this context this study investigates the long run growth of revenue and expenditure of the Government of Himachal Pradesh from 1999-00 to 2021-22. The annual average growth in different components of revenue account and capital account income and expenditure is calculated to understand the long run trends in finances of Government of Himachal Pradesh. The trend of the deficit of the budgets of the state government is studied in the recent decade to find out the reasons for increasing liabilities of the state government. The annual average growth in different components of revenue account and capital account income and expenditure, particularly expenditure on social and physical infrastructure.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature on state finances and its components particularly on infrastructure in India is presented below:

Ahluwalia, Isher Judge (1985) She examined the evidence of infrastructure constraint and the demand side impact of public investment on industrial growth in India from 1956-57 to 1979-80. The study point out that infrastructure bottlenecks in railways, electricity etc and insufficient management of these sectors are the important factors in affecting industrial growth in India.

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Ahluwalia, M. S. (1998) point out that improvement of growth performance of Indian economy in eighth plan and after will put demand pressure on power, roads, ports and airports after the initial slack in infrastructure is over. The author sees infrastructure as critical constraint on economic growth and underline the need for bold steps for private participation in infrastructure.

N. J. Kurian (1999) studied state government finances: a survey of recent trends. Study includes 15 major Indian states and concluded that there were substantial inter-state differences in the level of per capita income and their growth rates in recent years. The share of borrowing in plan financing was steadily going up in almost all states irrespective of their level of development. States own tax revenues and own non tax revenues were more important for relatively richer states, and share in central taxes and grants from center was more important for relatively poor states.

Nirupam, Bajpai and Jeffrey, D. Sachs (1999) examined the state of state government finances in India. Study revealed that fiscal deficits have remained high in the states, and a large component of these was made up of revenue deficits. Quite evidently, both expenditure and tax reforms have a long way to go in the states. The state expenditure-GDP ratio needs to be brought down considerably. The study also suggested that in present regime of subsidies there was need for reducing the overall scale of subsidies, making them transparent, and using them for well-defined economic objectives and focusing on final goods and services with a view to maximizing their impact on the targeted strata of the society at minimum cost, instituting systems for periodic reviews and setting clear limits on the duration of any new subsidy schemes.

Lekha Chakraborty and Kaushik K. Bhadra (2010) examined subnational public finance in times of recession. The article critically reviews the findings of the RBI study on state finances in 2009-10. The study points out that while few states announced stimulus packages to undertake investment in order to revive demand due to economic recession of 2008-09 and also announced tax concession, but the actual effect of the physical measures on overall imbalance appeared marginal. The quantum of physical stimulus packages' was not specified in states other than for Kerala, Haryana and west Bengal.

Kripa Shankar (2000) examined Parlous State of Government Finances. Study found that West Bengal's Loans and advances from the center constitute three-fourths of the state's outstanding liabilities. Whereas, growth rate in non-developmental expenditure at the state level was considerably higher than that of West Bengal.

Narayan, Luxmi (2015) analyzed recent trends in Haryana state finances on three broad indicators: revenue and spending patterns, resources gaps and debt sustainability. The time period of study was 2000-01 to 2013-14. The study found that state own tax revenue share has decreased and share of central transfer of taxes and grants to Haryana has showed increasing trends. The study suggested that state needs to increase its revenue base by following a prudent fiscal strategy by increasing its own tax non-tax revenue through user charges and by recovering cost from government services.

Shah and Joshi (2020) studied budgetary trends of Uttarakhand government an analysis of Almora district. The period of study was 2016-17 to 2019-20. The study found that budget was sufficiently allocated towards water supply, transport, Irrigation, sanitation and housing, social welfare and miscellaneous sector. Budget utilization was insufficient by sectors like medical and health, rural development, urban development and education sector. Budget allocated towards agriculture and allied services, energy and industry seems to be insufficient.

III. DATA

The data on budgets of the Government of Himachal Pradesh is collected from 1999-00 to 2021-22 from statistical abstracts of Himachal Pradesh. The component wise data on infrastructure is taken from economic activity wise GSDP of Himachal Pradesh from CSO and the Department of Economic and Statistics Himachal Pradesh. The data on deficit of the state government for the period of study is taken from state statistics and finances, RBI website.

IV. METHODOLOGY

To calculate the growth rate in different components of budget for the period 1999-00 to 2021-22 the annual average growth rate as well as compound growth rate method is used in the study. The long run trend is studied through best fit line estimated through regression. The growth of different components of the infrastructure is studied through linear regression model

V. REVENUE ACCOUNT RECEIPTS AND EXPENDITURE OF GOVERNMENT OF HIMACHAL PRADESH FROM 1999-00 TO 2021-22

Revenue account receipts for state own tax was rupees 549.38 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 9769.53 crore in the year 2021-22. Tax revenue, which was rupees 1299.36 crore in the year 1998-99, increased to rupees 15932.79 crore in the year 2021-22. Total tax revenue receipts was rupees 2311.93 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 37312.35 crore for the year.

Revenue expenditure for interest payment and debt services was rupees 551.92 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 4804.61 crore in the year 2021-22. Expenditure on education, sports and culture was rupees 533.04 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 7390.7 crore in the year 2021-22. Expenditure on health and family welfare was rupees 205.74 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 2900 crore in the year 2021-22. The net revenue expenditure was rupees 317.89 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupees 37034.24 crore in the year 2021-22.

Annual growth rate of revenue receipts which include state own tax (SOT), tax revenue (TRV), total revenue receipts (TRR) and revenue expenditure which include interest payment and debt services (IPD), education, sports and culture (ESC), health and family welfare (HFW), net revenue expenditure (NRE) are shown in Table 1.

The data reveals that annual average growth rate of state own tax revenue is 13.96 percent from period 1999-00 to 2021-22. State own tax revenue annual growth was highest at 48.52 percent for the year 2001-02. State own tax revenue annual growth rate was lowest at 0.97 percent in the year 2017-18. State own tax revenue annual growth rate displayed a declining linear trend in the long run.

The annual growth rate of tax revenue remains higher 55.92 percent for the year 2010-11. Whereas, annual average growth rate tax revenue remain lowest -31.31 percent for the year 2000-01. The data reveals that there is fluctuations in the state own tax revenue whereas the overall tax revenue was stable. The annual average growth rate of total tax revenue of the state is 12.63 percent during the period 1999-00 to 2021-22.

Tax revenue annual growth rate displayed a constant linear trend in the long run.

Table 1
Annual Growth Rate of Revenue Receipts and Expenditure

YEARS	Revenue Receipts			Revenue Expenditure			
	SOT	TRV	TRR	IPD	ESC	HFV	NRE
1999-00	7.23	18.62	60.70	8.23	54.03	20.46	21.40
2005-06	22.10	27.75	54.63	-11.12	13.79	17.75	11.66
2010-11	41.48	55.92	22.85	-0.31	29.78	25.15	18.79
2015-16	17.55	13.73	23.98	17.25	-9.34	-5.99	9.09
2020-21	0.98	1.22	3.43	-1.70	-12.48	-12.73	-7.71
2021-22	20.86	24.11	11.59	7.43	16.49	32.12	10.43
1999-2022	13.96	12.63	14.04	10.53	12.96	12.97	11.53

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of total revenue receipts for the whole period remains 14.04 percent. Annual growth rate of total revenue receipts remains highest 60.70 percent for the year 1999-00. Whereas, annual growth rate of total revenue receipts remains lowest -18.03 percent for the year 2000-01. The data on total revenue receipts shows less fluctuation than tax revenue and more fluctuation than state own taxes for the whole study period.

Total revenue receipts annual growth rate also displayed a declining linear trend in long run like state own tax. State own tax and total revenue receipts showed high degree of fluctuations than the total tax revenue. It shows deficient tax effort by the state.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The average annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on interest payment and debt service remained at 10.53 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on interest payment and debt service remains highest 22.64 percent for the year 2000-01. Whereas, the annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on interest payment and debt service remained lowest at -0.31 percent for the year 2010-11. The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on interest payment and debt service was fluctuating from 1999-00 to 2007-08 and after 2008-09 to 2021-22 it shows less fluctuation.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on interest payment and debt service displayed a declining trend in long run. It means increasing liabilities of the state government in successive years.

The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on education, sports and culture was highest at 54.03 for the year 1999-00. Whereas, annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on education, sports and culture remains lowest at -12.48 for the year 2020-21. The annual average growth rate of revenue expenditure on education, sports and culture remains for the whole period remains 12.96 percent. The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on education, sports and culture shows fluctuations for the whole period.

The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on education, sports and culture displayed a declining trend in long run.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of revenue expenditure on health and family welfare remains 12.97 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on health and family welfare remains highest 38.11 percent for the year 2014-15. Whereas, annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on health and family welfare remains lowest -12.73 for the year 2020-21. The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on health and family welfare shows greater fluctuation after the year 2010-11.

The annual growth rate of revenue expenditure on health and family welfare displayed an increasing trend in the long run.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual growth rate of net revenue expenditure remains highest 23.47 percent for the year 2019-20. Whereas, annual growth rate of net revenue expenditure was lowest at -7.71 percent for the year 2020-21.

The annual average growth rate of rate of net revenue expenditure shows high fluctuations after the year 2018-19. The annual average growth rate of rate of net revenue expenditure displayed a minor declining trend in long run.

The broad results from above analysis show slower growth in revenue of the state and faster growth in the expenditure of the state. Some component like health shows greater growth in expenditure relative to other component like education. Given this trend the liabilities of the state government is likely to increase in future.

VI. CAPITAL ACCOUNT RECEIPTS AND EXPENDITURE

The capital receipts was rupee 3057.24 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 12913.8 crore for the year 2021-22. Capital expenditure on general services was rupee 14.57 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 360.06 crore for the year 2021-22. Expenditure on social service was rupee 128.98 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 2037.01 crore for the year 2021-22. Expenditure on economic services was rupee 403.47 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 4772.55 crore for the year 2021-22.

Annual growth rate of capital receipts (CAR) and capital expenditure which include general service (GEN), social services (SOS), economic services (ECS) and total expenditure (TEP) are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Annual Growth Rate of Capital Account Receipts and Expenditure

Capital Receipts		Capital Expenditure			
YEARS	CAR	GES	SOS	ECS	TEP
1999-00	53.17	131.84	55.81	-6.21	15.38
2005-06	-17.38	141.18	45.43	30.90	40.22
2010-11	19.97	20.14	-6.25	-14.89	-11.22
2015-16	-42.86	6.09	47.43	4.40	13.42
2020-21	44.07	-34.80	26.42	-20.78	-10.59
2021-22	-23.36	100.58	17.33	37.92	33.24
1999-2022	13.11	25.24	15.54	14.35	13.61

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of capital receipts was 13.11 percent from 1999-00 to 2021-22. The annual growth rate of capital receipts was highest at 53.17 percent for the year 1999-00. Whereas, annual growth rate of capital receipts remains lowest -42.86 percent for the year 2015-16.

The annual growth rate of capital receipts was stable between 2004-05 to 2009-10 and highly unstable after the year 2010-11. The annual growth rate of capital receipts displayed an increasing trend in long run.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of capital expenditure for general services remains 25.24 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rate of capital expenditure for general services remains highest 154.31 percent for the year 2016-17. Whereas, the annual growth rate of capital expenditure on general services remained lowest at -57.97 percent for the year 2001-02. The expenditure on general services was highly unstable for the whole study period.

The expenditure on general services displayed a constant trend in long run same as the annual average of the capital expenditure for general services. It shows that the expenditure on general services is growing at stable rate.

Figure 11. Annual Growth Rate of Social Services (SOS) from 1999-00 to 2021-22

Figure 12. Annual Growth Rate of Economic Services (ECS) from 1999-00 to 2021-22

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual growth rate of capital expenditure for social services was highest at 55.81 percent for the year 1999-00. Whereas, annual growth rate of capital expenditure for social services remained lowest at -34.93 percent for the year 2011-12. The annual average growth rate of capital expenditure for social services remains 15.54 percent for the whole study period.

The growth in expenditure on social services was fluctuating for the whole study period. The growth in expenditure on social services displayed a declining trend in long run. The result shows the expenditure on social services is maintained.

The annual average growth rate of capital expenditure for economic services remains 14.35 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rates of capital expenditure for economic services remain highest at 61.99 percent for the year 2002-03. Whereas, the annual growth rate of capital expenditure for economic services remained lowest at -30.16 percent for the year 2004-05.

The expenditure on economic services was also highly unstable like general and social services for whole the study period. The expenditure on economic services displayed an increasing trend in long run. The result shows that the expenditure on economic services is rising in successive years.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of total capital expenditure remains 13.61 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rates of total capital expenditure remain highest 41.92 percent for the year 2008-09. Whereas, the annual growth rate of total capital expenditure was lowest at -23.67 percent for the year 2004-05.

The expenditure on total capital expenditure was also fluctuating, like previous three sectors (General, Social and Economic) for whole the study period. The expenditure on total capital expenditure displayed an increasing trend in long run.

The result from above analysis of capital account growth shows that income is maintained but expenditure is rising continuously although with fluctuations. It means greater liabilities of the state government in the coming years.

VII. EXPENDITURE ON PHYSICAL AND SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE FROM BUDGETS OF THE GOVERNMENT OF HIMACHAL PRADESH FROM 1999-00 TO 2021-22

The expenditure on social infrastructure was rupee 738.79 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 10290.70 crore to 2021-22. Expenditure on physical infrastructure was rupee 333.80 crore for the year 1998-99 which increased to rupee 4468.09 crore to 2021-22.

Annual growth rate of revenue account expenditure on social infrastructure (SIF) and physical infrastructure (PIF) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Annual Growth Rate infrastructure Expenditure

YEARS	Infrastructure Expenditure	
	SIF(Social Infrastructure)	PIF(Physical Infrastructure)
1999-00	44.68	26.84
2005-06	14.67	37.44
2010-11	28.73	18.11
2015-16	-8.56	9.41
2020-21	-12.55	-1.51
2021-22	20.51	-2.75
1999-2022	12.88	12.82

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The annual average growth rate of expenditure on social infrastructure remains 12.88 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rates of expenditure on social infrastructure remain highest 44.88 percent for the year 1999-00. Whereas, annual growth rate of expenditure on social infrastructure remains lowest at -12.55 percent for the year 2020-21.

Figure 14. Social Infrastructure (SIF) Growth Rate from 1999-00 to 2021-22

Figure 15. Physical Infrastructure (PIF) Growth Rate from 1999-00 to 2021-22

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The growth in expenditure on social infrastructure expenditure was highly unstable for the whole study period. The growth in expenditure on social infrastructure expenditure displayed a declining trend for long run.

The annual average growth rate of expenditure on physical infrastructure remains 12.82 percent for the whole study period. The annual growth rates of expenditure on physical infrastructure remain highest at 46.27 percent for the year 2007-08. Whereas, the annual growth rate of expenditure on physical infrastructure remains lowest at -5.56 percent for the year 2011-12.

The growth in expenditure on physical infrastructure shows fluctuations like social infrastructure for whole the study period. The expenditure physical infrastructure expenditure displayed a declining trend in the long run.

The above results shows that expenditure on physical and social infrastructure is although increasing in successive years but it shows declining growth, which means budget is more skewed towards revenue account expenditure.

VIII. FISCAL, REVENUE AND PRIMARY DEFICIT IN BUDGETS OF GOVERNMENT OF HIMACHAL PRADESH FROM 2004-05 TO 2020-21

The gross fiscal deficit was rupee 1810 crore for the year 2004-05 which increased to rupee 6993 crore for the year 2020-21. Revenue account deficit was rupee 1158 crore for the year 2004-05 which declined to rupee 545 crore for the year 2020-21. Primary account deficit was rupee 169 crore for the year 2004-05 which increased to rupee 2370 crore for the year 2020-21.

The gross fiscal account deficit (GFD), revenue account deficit (RVD) and primary account deficit (PRD) of Government of Himachal Pradesh are shown in Table 4.

As shown in Table 4 gross fiscal deficit is continually increasing from 2004-05 to 2020-21 that is from 1810 crore to 6993 crore.

The long run trend line of gross fiscal deficit displays increasing trend.

Table 4

Fiscal, Revenue and Primary Deficit in Crore from 2004-05 to 2020-21

YEARS	GFD	RVD	PRD
2004-05	1810	1158	169
2009-10	2784	805	828
2014-15	4200	1944	1351
2019-20	5602	-8	1368
2020-21	6993	545	2370

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The revenue account deficit was highest in the year 2014-15 (that is rupee 1944 crore). It was lowest in the year 2018-19 (that is rupee -1522 crore), which means that for the year 2018-19 there was no revenue account deficit (rupees 1522 crore surplus).

The long run trend line of revenue account deficit is displaying a decreasing tendency.

The primary account deficit was lowest for the year 2007-08 that is rupee -1151 crore. It was highest for the year 2020-21 that is rupee 2370 crore. The primary account deficit was continuously increasing from 2004-05 to 2020-21.

The primary account deficit displayed an increasing trend in long run like gross fiscal deficit as shown in the Figure No. 16 below.

Source: Authors calculations from various Statistical Abstracts of Himachal Pradesh

The above results of deficit shows that the state is heavily borrowing to meet its expenditure, it means growing liabilities in successive budgets.

IX. CONCLUSION

The study of recent two decades of growth of finances of Government of Himachal Pradesh shows growing liabilities in revenue account as well as capital account in the successive budgets. The results shows that the revenue receipts is growing with declining trend whereas revenue account expenditure showing fluctuations and stable increasing trend, particularly the expenditure on health and family welfare. The capital account income is maintained and expenditure is rising with fluctuations. It means greater liabilities of the state government in coming years. The expenditure on physical and social infrastructure is although increasing in successive years but it shows declining growth, which means budget, is more skewed towards revenue account expenditure. The long term trends of deficit shows that the state is heavily borrowing to meet its expenditure, thereby increasing its liabilities.

Unless greater tax efforts and increase in economic activities in agriculture and industrial sector is undertaken, the growing fiscal deficit will lead to greater liabilities particularly interest and principal amount in coming years.

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IX. CONCLUSION

The study of recent two decades of growth of finances of Government of Uttarakhand shows that the revenue receipts are growing with declining rate whereas revenue expenditure is showing fluctuations and stable increasing trend. The expenditure on health and family welfare, the capital account item is maintained and expenditure is rising with fast pace. It means greater liabilities of the state government in coming years. The expenditure on physical and social infrastructure is although increasing in successive years but it shows declining growth which means budget is more of need-oriented revenue account expenditure. The long term trend of revenue shows that the state is heavily borrowing to meet its expenditure, thereby increasing its liability. Latest fiscal year shows that the state is heavily borrowing to meet its expenditure, thereby increasing its liability. The growing fiscal deficit will lead to a high level of borrowing in future and thereby amount in coming years.